

Search for New Anthelmintics - Part III Synthesis of Substituted Dithiocarbamic Acid Esters

S. S. TIWARI and (MISS) SUMAN BALA MISRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow

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Several newer derivatives of dithiocarbamates with ethyl chlorides of secondary amines have been prepared, with a view to evaluate their anthelmintic activity. Out of 23 compounds synthesized 7 compounds were tested for anthelmintic, amoebicidal and antitubercular activity, however, none of the compound possessed significant activity.

THE Pharmacological activity of piperazine as anthelmintic is well known¹⁻², further, 1,4-disubstituted piperazines have been claimed to be more potent than piperazine viz., 1,4-diphenyl-piperazine, 1,4-dibenzyl piperazine and 1,4-dicyclohexyl piperazine causing irreversible paralysis of the parasite³ without an initial period of excitation. Riedel *et al.*⁴ have demonstrated that dithiocarbamates are effective as filaricides.

Thus in order to prepare broad spectrum anthelmintic agents it was considered worthwhile to prepare piperazine-1,4- (substituted ethyl dithio carbamic acid esters).

Secondary amines viz., morpholine and piperidine have been found to possess marked anthelmintic activity, therefore authors have also synthesized several derivatives of substituted-ethyl dithiocarbamic acid esters of secondary amines.

Synthesis :

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries in H₂SO₄ melting point bath and are uncorrected.

Dithiocarbamates : Various dithiocarbamates were prepared following the method of Tokuda *et al.*⁵

Ethyl chloride hydrochlorides of secondary amines : These were prepared by various methods.

1-piperidino ethyl chloride hydrochloride, and 4-morpholino ethyl chloride hydrochloride were prepared according to the method of Wadia *et al.*⁶

β (1-pyrrolidyl) ethyl chloride hydrochloride was prepared according to the method of Wright *et al.*⁷ while β -diethyl amino ethyl chloride hydrochloride and β -dimethyl amino ethyl chloride hydrochloride were prepared following the method of Breslow *et al.*⁸

Substituted ethyl chlorides were prepared from respective ethyl chloride hydrochlorides by the method of Breslow *et al.*⁸ To (1.75 mole) appropriate ethyl chloride hydrochloride was added 100 g

of crushed ice and the mixture covered with 400 ml of ether, keeping the temperature at 5°, a cold solution of 70 g of sodium-hydroxide in 150 ml of water was added with stirring, the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for several minutes. The ether layer was separated and dried over anhydrous Magnesium Sulphate. The ether was removed under reduced pressure leaving behind substituted ethyl chloride as a red oil. This was used as such.

Preparation of Piperazine 1,4-(substituted ethyl dithio carbamic acid esters):

To a solution of substituted ethyl chloride in dry acetone (0.2 mole) piperazine 1,4 (Sod dithio carbamate (0.1 mole) was added. The resultant solution was stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr, after that it was poured over 100 g of crushed ice and allowed to stand for 1 hr at room temperature. Fine crystals which separated out were recrystallised from alcohol.

Preparation of substituted ethyl dithiocarbamic acid esters :

These were prepared by refluxing substituted ethyl chloride (0.1 mole) and appropriate dithio carbamate (0.1 mole) in dry acetone for 24 hr on a steam bath. The syrupy liquid that was obtained after removal of acetone was taken up in ether. The ether layer was washed successively with 5% NaOH solution and water and then dried over anhydrous magnesium-sulphate. Ether was distilled off and the solid was recrystallised from dry benzene giving very fine crystals.

Compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 1 and Table 2.

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TABLE 1—PIPERAZINE 1,4(SUBSTITUTED ETHYL DITHIO CARBAMIC ACID ESTERS)

Com- pound no.	R	Yield %	M.P. °C	Composition	Nitrogen		Analysis %	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Sulphur Found
1.	morpholino	75	175	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₄	12.06	11.91	27.54	27.48
2.	pyrrolidino	70	160	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ N ₄ S ₄	12.96	12.62	29.63	29.11
*3.	piperidino	78	141	C ₂₀ H ₃₆ N ₄ S ₄	12.17	11.92	27.82	27.89
*4.	diethylamino	80	105	C ₁₈ H ₃₆ N ₄ S ₄	12.84	12.85	29.35	28.99
5.	dimethylamino	70	193	C ₄ H ₂₈ N ₄ S ₄	14.73	14.07	33.68	33.07

TABLE 2—SUBSTITUTED ETHYL DITHIOCARBAMIC ACID ESTER

com- pound No.	R	R'	Yield %	M.P. °C	Composition	Nitrogen		Analysis %	
						Calcd	Found	Calcd.	Sulphur Found
1.	morpholino	morpholino	40	95	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	10.14	9.81	23.18	22.88
*2.	morpholino	piperidino	40	45	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	10.21	9.78	23.35	23.25
*3.	morpholino	diethylamine	45	50	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	10.68	10.28	24.42	23.94
4.	morpholino	dimethylamine	40	60	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O	11.96	11.78	27.35	27.12
*5.	piperidino	morpholino	48	52	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	10.21	9.84	23.35	23.20
*6.	piperidino	piperidino	40	66	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	10.29	9.98	23.52	22.98
7.	piperidino	diethylamino	45	88	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	10.76	10.55	24.61	24.01
8.	piperidino	dimethylamino	48	100	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	12.06	11.95	27.58	27.08
9.	diethylamino	morpholino	42	132	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	10.68	10.56	24.42	24.02
10.	diethylamino	piperidino	45	135	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	10.76	10.72	24.61	24.12
11.	diethylamino	diethylamino	45	300-301	C ₁₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ S ₂	11.29	11.48	25.80	25.50
12.	diethylamino	dimethylamino	40	100	C ₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	12.72	12.81	29.09	29.21
*13.	dimethylamino	morpholino	45	130	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O	11.96	11.76	27.35	27.02
14.	dimethylamino	piperidino	40	110	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	12.06	12.12	27.58	26.98
15.	dimethylamino	diethylamino	40	143	C ₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂	12.72	12.52	29.09	29.02
16.	dimethylamino	dimethylamino	45	141	C ₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	14.58	14.08	33.33	33.24
17.	pyrrolidino	morpholino	45	130	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ O	10.76	10.58	24.61	24.46
18.	pyrrolidino	piperidino	48	140	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂	10.85	10.58	24.80	24.22

All the melting points are uncorrected. Compounds marked with asterisk in Table 1 and Table 2 were tested for anthelmintic activity against *Hymenolepis nana* at the dose of 250 mg/kg in rats, no significant activity was noted, also none of the compound was found to possess amoebicidal and antitubercular activity.

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